

Thermal and mechanical analysis of Li-ion battery fire containment

Sindhu Bushpalli, Changmin Cao, Gearoid Clancy, Hariharan Kallath, El Hassan Ridouane

Problem statement

Vision

- Battery systems in aircrafts play significant role in reducing environmental footprint
- Modular and scalable technologies support multiple market segments
- High energy density batteries are required for all systems
- Significant certification risks related to **safety & containing cell failures**

Scope

- Thermal Runaway modelling of battery pack solutions
- Develop light-weight and safe composite battery containment
- Proof-of-Concept testing of integrated battery pack solutions

Li-ion battery containment overview

- Contain thermal runaway while retaining structural integrity
- Weight savings: light weight materials – different composite configurations
- Limit box outside temperature and reduce thermal risk to other systems
- Evaluate performance: Cone calorimetry testing, UL2596
- Develop and validate numerical models

UL solutions battery enclosure lab

Thermal analysis of composite solution

- Collins composite material thermal model was validated using test data. Composite material selection was completed and candidates with better performance were identified, and full module tests are planned.

Structural analysis

Next Steps and Challenges

- Coupon level testing planned for several material configurations
- Testing small scale demonstrator – few cells in thermal runaway
- Develop and validate numerical models using test data

Results